

Innovative sensors (first release)

SPOKE 4 – Digital innovation toward sustainable mountain

DELIVERABLE DN.7

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	24/03/2024	First Draft	Ferraris S.
0.5	26/03/2024	Second Draft	Ferraris S.
0.9	28/03/2024	Conclusion and Dataset	Ferraris S.
1	29/03/2024	Final edit	Bosio R.

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

Contents

NODES Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile	1
NODES – NORD OVEST DIGITALE E SOSTENIBILE	1
<i>VERSION HISTORY</i>	<i>1</i>
GLOSSARY	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
A) PROCEDURE FOR ASSESSING THE WATER BALANCE OF A MOUNTAIN BASIN WITH A SIGNIFICANT SNOW CONTRIBUTION USING INNOVATIVE SENSORS	3
INTRODUCTION	4
METHODOLOGY	4
<i>The Innovative Procedure.....</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>Experimental sites.....</i>	<i>8</i>

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A) Procedure for assessing the water balance of a mountain basin with a

significant snow contribution using innovative sensors

Introduction

In mountain catchments, it is particularly complicated to quantify the availability of water resources due to the significant variability of snow supply, especially at high altitudes. Remote sensing is not yet able to effectively quantify the water equivalent of the snow cover and the flow rates in streams. However, it is advantageous to evaluate the area covered by snow. The monitoring network of the regional Functional Centers provides the flow rates of the watercourses in real-time, even with a frequency of less than an hour, but only in basins of significant territorial surface area. Instead, the present procedure focuses on smaller contributing basins, especially where the snow supply is significant and there is a considerable flow rate increase during the springs (Figure 4, station in the Nivolet area). In these situations, there are significant effects on critical sectors of the mountain economy, such as hydroelectric, hydro-potable and ski resorts (subject to verification of the minimum ecological runoff in the withdrawals for electricity and/or programmed snow).

Methodology

The Innovative Procedure

This document describes an innovative procedure for integrating data from the regional functional centres with data acquired through an innovative monitoring network consisting of:

1. Time Domain Reflectometry technique with a low-cost commercial instrument weighing 400g and therefore transportable by personnel in the area (also descending with ski), together with self-produced probes (see Previati et al., 2011) (Figure 1) for snow water equivalent (SWE) measurements;
2. Continuous snow level measurements with low-cost Arduino technology in locations without electricity and telephone coverage (Figure 2);
3. Flow meters with automatic injection of NaCl saline solution (Figure 3);
4. Arduino low-cost technology for continuously monitoring watercourse levels (and therefore flow rate), electrical conductivity and water temperature. These last two measurements are used to quantify the flow dynamics, with particular reference to the base flow (Gentile et al., 2023, Gentile et al., 2024)(Figure 4 and Figure 5);
5. LICOR 710 evapotranspiration flow meter (the comparison meter is visible in Figure 6);
6. Real-time disdrometer sensor to divide the solid and liquid contributions of precipitation (Figure 6).

Figure 1 - Measurements with prototypal TDR version for snow water equivalent in the spring 2023.

Figure 2 - Continuous snow level meters with low-cost Arduino technology in two locations at the top and at a median altitude in the catchment; they are without electricity and telephone coverage (Bussoleno, Valle di Susa).

Figure 3 - Flow measurement instrument the 10th of April 2024 after 7 months operation (Olen catchment, Alagna Val Sesia, VC).

Figure 4 - Measuring station in a mountain stream (Acceglio, Maira valley, CN) for flow, electrical conductivity and temperature.

Figure 5. Instrumentation for actual evapotranspiration flows, equipped with a real-time disdrometer sensor to divide precipitation's solid and liquid contributions (Nivolet, Valsavarenche, AO).

Figure 6. Flow rate, electrical conductivity and temperature trend in stream and spring at an altitude of 2550 meters (Nivolet, Valsavarenche, AO).

Through this integrated network of innovative sensors (see Figure 7), it is possible to quantify the water supply in small basins that are not monitored by regional functional centres, providing information such as real-time flow and current SWE at altitude, which is essential for crucial sectors of the mountain economy.

Figure 7. Measurement scheme in the whole catchment

Experimental sites

All the mentioned instruments are employed in the two following main catchments:

- **forest in Bussoleno (TO)** (49 07 06 N 7 09 47 E 2050 to 650 m asl);
- **high-altitude grassland (Nivolet, Valsavarenche, AO)** (45 31 07 N 7 10 16 E 3400 to 2550 m asl);

with the exception of the saline solution discharge sensor, which have been employed from the beginning of September in the high-altitude grassland of **Olen catchment (Alagna Valsesia, VC)** (45 51 55 N 7 54 06 E 3020 to 2050 m asl.). This location has been selected due to the main interest of Monterosa 2000 (ski area) in the ecological minimum flow and in combination with measurements of other research groups.

A second NaCl saline solution sensor will soon be installed at the Bussoleno site.

The EC, T and discharge sensor has also been installed in the **grassland and forest Maurin catchment Maira Valley (CN)** (44 29 52 N 6 55 11 E 3390 to 1630 m asl) in a hydroelectric exploitation.

First Output

Cosmic ray data.

Data coming from Cosmic Ray can be used, during the snow season, as comparison of snow water equivalent (SWE) with TDR data mentioned above. During the rest of the year Cosmic Ray can provide soil moisture data. The data of Nivolet site for both SWE and soil moisture are shown in figure 8.

Figure 8. Cosmic ray measurement scheme at the Nivolet site.

Geophysical data.

The group of DIATI department (POITO) in March 2024 has done two campaigns in the Bussoleno site for evaluating the groundwater reservoir. It is a crucial information for understanding the catchment water dynamics. The data collected and a metafile are also enclosed. A preliminary graph is here included in figure 9. The values 500 – 600 ohm (dark blue) are a signal of water presence. The yellow colour is giving instead unsaturated formations, probably with old landslide boulders.

Figure 9. Electrical resistance tomography at the Bussoleno site.

Data

The first water balance data obtained through this innovative procedure have been collected in a special dataset that can be viewed at the following [address](#), with limited access pending publication of an article about it.

The dataset contain the following data:

- Cosmic ray Snow Water Equivalent data at Nivolet site (they will be compared in the next month with TDR measurements);
- Snow depth at Nivolet site at 30 minutes interval;
- Olen catchment Salt measurement of discharge (raw conductivity data);
- Bussoleno and Nivolet stream Electrical Conductivity, Temperature, water depth data at 10 minutes interval;
- Actual evapotranspiration at Bussoleno and Nivolet sites at 30 minutes interval;
- Disdrometer precipitation classification data at Nivolet site at 1 minute interval;
- ERT geophysical data with metafile explanation.

Conclusion

In the first part of the projet instruments have been bought and tested, collecting a huge amount of data in four different provinces of NW Italy. Some of these data have been already processed, showing the possible operativity in the water resources assessment in mountain catchments. Some published scientific papers have shown the theoretical background for the development of an innovative procedure. Also, the stream and springs water conductivity data will allow to better understand the geophysical ERT results.